

Aliphatic Chains as Physical Realizations of One-Dimensional Spin Chains Supporting Magnetically Silent Spin Waves

Calculation of spin-chain zero-quantum NMR for aliphatic chains with $n = 4$ CH₂ groups, 8-spin system

Simulation Parameters

```
Spins = {1 / 2, 1 / 2, 1 / 2, 1 / 2, 1 / 2, 1 / 2, 1 / 2, 1 / 2};
(*The program can calculate spin-1/2 and spin-
 1 nuclei. Here we set 8 spins 1/2 as the spin system*)
NspinsOneHalf = Length@Select[Spins, # == 1 / 2 &];
NspinsOne = Length@Select[Spins, # == 1 &];
Nspins = NspinsOne + NspinsOneHalf;

In[*]:= (* J-Couplings in an idealized aliphatic chain*)
Jintra := -14.0; (*Intrapair J-
 coupling between two geminal protons. It is important to add .0 after each number,
 this is important for normalization of the eigenvectors*)
Jvic1 = 5.0;
Jvic2 = 10.0;
```

Initializes functions to generate spin-matrices, Hamiltonians, Rotation matrices.

```
In[*]:= imax = 2NspinsOneHalf * 3NspinsOne; (*The size of Hilbert space*)
```

```
In[*]:=  $\sigma = \left\{ \left\{ \{1, 0\}, \{0, 1\} \right\}, \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \{0, 1\}, \{1, 0\} \right\}, \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \{0, -1\}, \{1, 0\} \right\}, \right.$ 
 $\frac{1}{2} \left\{ \{1, 0\}, \{0, -1\} \right\}, \left\{ \{1, 0, 0\}, \{0, 1, 0\}, \{0, 0, 1\} \right\},$ 
 $\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \left\{ \{0, 1, 0\}, \{1, 0, 1\}, \{0, 1, 0\} \right\}, \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2 \text{I}} \left\{ \{0, 1, 0\}, \{-1, 0, 1\}, \{0, -1, 0\} \right\},$ 
 $\left. \left\{ \{1, 0, 0\}, \{0, 0, 0\}, \{0, 0, -1\} \right\} \right\};$  (*Constructing Bloch matrices*)
```

MatrixForm /@ σ

```
Out[*]:=  $\left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\frac{i}{2} \\ \frac{i}{2} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}, \right.$ 
 $\left. \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 \\ \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & -\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ 
```

```
In[*]:= (*Setting up the Zeeman basis. All the matrix representations
of spin operators are initially calculated on this basis*)
```

```
In[*]:= ZeemanBasis := Module[{ner, tmp, MzQuantumNumbers, i, basis},
  MzQuantumNumbers = {{0, 0}, {0, 0}};
  For[i = 1, i ≤ Nspins, i++,
    tmp = Table[s, {s, Spins[[i]}, -Spins[[i]}, -1];
    MzQuantumNumbers = Insert[MzQuantumNumbers, tmp, 2 + i];
  ];
  MzQuantumNumbers = Drop[MzQuantumNumbers, 2];
  basis = Tuples[MzQuantumNumbers];
  basis]
(* basis is the uncoupled Zeeman basis *)
```

```
In[*]:= ZeemanBasis;
```

```
In[*]:= (*Creating a set of all matrix representations of the Cartesian spin operators
(e.g. I1x, I1y, I1z, I2x, etc) in the form of IOps[spin,axis]. Indeces
for axis are labeled as following: 1 - x, y - 2, z - 3*)
```

```

In[ ]:= IOps = ConstantArray[0, {Nspins, 3}];

For[i = 1, i ≤ Nspins, i++,
  For[j = 1, j ≤ 3, j++,
    list1 = Table[KroneckerDelta[s, i], {s, 1, Nspins}];
    Which[Max[list1 * Spins] == 1 / 2,
      list1 = (j + 1) * list1, (*the first element is unity matrix,
        which we don't need, so j+1 runs from 2(x),
        3(y) to 4(z)Pauli matrices for spin 1/2. Similar with spin 1 -
        skipping the first elements and starting with 6(x),7(y),8(z)*)
      Max[list1 * Spins] == 1,
      list1 = (j + 5) * list1
    ];
    list2 =
      (ConstantArray[1, {Nspins}] - Table[KroneckerDelta[s, i], {s, 1, Nspins}]) * Spins;

    For[k = 1, k ≤ Nspins, k++,
      Which[list2[[k]] == 1 / 2,
        list2[[k]] = 1,
        list2[[k]] == 1,
        list2[[k]] = 5
      ];

      ];
    list1 = list1 + list2;
    IOps[[i, j]] = σ[list1[[1]]];
    If[Nspins > 1,
      For[k = 2, k ≤ Nspins, k++,
        IOps[[i, j]] = KroneckerProduct[IOps[[i, j]], σ[list1[[k]]]];
      ];];
  ];

In[ ]:= (*Total spin operators*)

In[ ]:= Ixtot := Sum[IOps[[j, 1]], {j, 1, Nspins}];
Iytot := Sum[IOps[[j, 2]], {j, 1, Nspins}];
Iztot := Sum[IOps[[j, 3]], {j, 1, Nspins}];

In[ ]:= (*Instantaneous hard pulses*)

In[ ]:= (Rx[β_] := MatrixExp[-I β Sum[IOps[[i, 1]], {i, 1, Nspins}]]);
(Ry[β_] := MatrixExp[-I β Sum[IOps[[i, 2]], {i, 1, Nspins}]]);
(Rφ[φ_, β_] :=
  MatrixExp[-I β Sum[Cos[φ] IOps[[i, 1]] + Sin[φ] IOps[[i, 2]], {i, 1, Nspins}]]);

```

```

In[ ]:= (*Deriving equation for expectation values
(in case of 3x3 matrices) used in the trajectory functions below*)
H = {u1, u2, u3}; (*Hamiltonian*)
R = {{r11, r12, r13}, {r21, r22, r23}, {r31, r32, r33}}; (*density matrix*)
Q = {{q11, q12, q13}, {q21, q22, q23}, {q31, q32, q33}};
(*observation operator for which the expectation value is taken*)
Tr[DiagonalMatrix[Exp[-I H]].R.DiagonalMatrix[Exp[I H]].Q] // FullSimplify
Sum[Exp[-I H[[a]]] * Exp[I H[[b]]] * R[[a, b]] * Q[[b, a]], {a, 1, 3}, {b, 1, 3}] // FullSimplify
Sum[Exp[-I (H[[a]] - H[[b]])] * R[[a, b]] * Q[[b, a]], {a, 1, 3}, {b, 1, 3}] // FullSimplify

Out[ ]:= q11 r11 + e-i (u1-u2) q21 r12 + e-i (u1-u3) q31 r13 + ei (u1-u2) q12 r21 +
q22 r22 + e-i (u2-u3) q32 r23 + ei (u1-u3) q13 r31 + ei (u2-u3) q23 r32 + q33 r33

Out[ ]:= q11 r11 + e-i (u1-u2) q21 r12 + e-i (u1-u3) q31 r13 + ei (u1-u2) q12 r21 +
q22 r22 + e-i (u2-u3) q32 r23 + ei (u1-u3) q13 r31 + ei (u2-u3) q23 r32 + q33 r33

Out[ ]:= q11 r11 + e-i (u1-u2) q21 r12 + e-i (u1-u3) q31 r13 + ei (u1-u2) q12 r21 +
q22 r22 + e-i (u2-u3) q32 r23 + ei (u1-u3) q13 r31 + ei (u2-u3) q23 r32 + q33 r33

In[ ]:= (*The function below calculates the expectation value at time t of an input Operator
in the density matrix ρ. Both matrices of the Operator and of the density
matrix should be set in the eigenbasis of the Hamiltonian. eigenfreqs is a
list of eigenfrequencies of the Hamiltonian under which evolution occurs.*)

In[ ]:= ExpectationValue [ρ_, Operator_, eigenfreqs_, t_] :=

Parallelize[Sum[Exp[-I (Chop[eigenfreqs[[a]] - eigenfreqs[[b]])] t] *
Chop[ρ[[a, b]] * Operator[[b, a]], {a, 1, imax}, {b, 1, imax}]] // ExpToTrig // Chop

In[ ]:= (*The function below calculates the transformation matrix from Zeeman direct product
basis to direct product of singlet-triplet states for an even number of spins*)

In[ ]:= TransformToSingletTripletBasis[Nspins_] := Module[{STMatrix, N, STTransform},

If[EvenQ[Nspins],

STMatrix =
{{0, 1/√2, -1/√2, 0}, {1, 0, 0, 0}, {0, 1/√2, 1/√2, 0}, {0, 0, 0, 1}};
N = Nspins / 2;
STTransform = STMatrix;
If[Nspins ≥ 4,
For[i = 1, i ≤ N - 1, i++,

STTransform = KroneckerProduct[STTransform, STMatrix]
];

];
STTransform
]
]

```

```
In[*]:= (*The function below calculates a matrix that permutes the states sorted according to
gerade/ungerade manifolds and according to the total z projection. This function
works only for spin systems consisting only of spins-1/2 but not of spins-1*)
```

```
In[*]:= SortByMz[VectorStates_, Nspins_] :=
Module[{Npairs, Nstates, PermutationMatrix, tmpblock,
  tmp, Mz, nProjections, SortedStates, i, j, k, l, Nsinglets},

  Npairs = Nspins / 2;
  Nstates = Length[VectorStates];
  nProjections = Nspins + 1; (*This is only applicable for spin-1/2*)
  Mz = 0;
  PermutationMatrix = ConstantArray[0, {Nstates, Nstates}];
  SortedStates = VectorStates;
  tmpblock = 0;
  tmp = 1;
  Nsinglets = 0;

  If[EvenQ[Nspins],
    For[l = 0, l ≤ Npairs, l++,
      For[i = nProjections, Abs[i] ≤ nProjections, i--,
        For[j = 1, j ≤ Nstates, j++,
          Mz = 0;
          Nsinglets = 0;
          For[k = 1, k ≤ Npairs, k++,
            Which[VectorStates[[j]][[k]] == "Tp", Mz = Mz + 1,
              VectorStates[[j]][[k]] == "T0", Mz = Mz + 0, VectorStates[[j]][[k]] == "Tm",
                Mz = Mz - 1, VectorStates[[j]][[k]] == "S", Mz = Mz + 0];
            If[VectorStates[[j]][[k]] == "S",
              Nsinglets = Nsinglets + 1;
            ];
          ];
        ];
      If[EvenQ[l] && Mz == i && Nsinglets == 1, (*Even number of singlets*)
        SortedStates[[tmp]] = VectorStates[[j]];
        PermutationMatrix[[tmp]][[j]] = 1;
        tmp = tmp + 1;
      ];
    ];
  ];
```

```
For[l = 0, l ≤ Npairs, l++,
  For[i = nProjections, Abs[i] ≤ nProjections, i--,
    For[j = 1, j ≤ Nstates, j++,
      Mz = 0;
      Nsinglets = 0;
      For[k = 1, k ≤ Npairs, k++,
        Which[VectorStates[[j]][[k]] == "Tp", Mz = Mz + 1,
          VectorStates[[j]][[k]] == "T0", Mz = Mz + 0, VectorStates[[j]][[k]] == "Tm",
```

```

    Mz = Mz - 1, VectorStates[[j]][k] == "S", Mz = Mz + 0];
    If[VectorStates[[j]][k] == "S",
      Nsinglets = Nsinglets + 1;
    ];
  ];
  If[OddQ[1] && Mz == i && Nsinglets == 1, (*Odd number of singlets*)
    SortedStates[tmp] = VectorStates[[j]];
    PermutationMatrix[tmp][j] = 1;
    tmp = tmp + 1;
  ]
]
];
];
{PermutationMatrix, SortedStates}
]

In[ ]:= STBasisTransform = TransformToSingletTripletBasis[Nspins];

In[ ]:= (*Setting up singlet-triplet product basis and sorting it*)

In[ ]:= NspinPairs = Nspins / 2;
LST = Tuples[{"S", "Tp", "T0", "Tm"}, NspinPairs];
{MzTransform, StatesMz} = SortByMz[LST, Nspins];

In[ ]:= (*Setting up a function to calculate Hamiltonian
Hj for 4 CH2 groups (see eq. 4 of the main text).*)

In[ ]:= HamIdealized[Jintra_, ΣJ_, ΔJ_] := Module[{H},

  H = 2 π (
    Jintra Sum [IOps[[1, i]].IOps[[2, i]], {i, 1, 3}] +
    Jintra Sum [IOps[[3, i]].IOps[[4, i]], {i, 1, 3}] + Jintra Sum [IOps[[5, i]].IOps[[6, i]],
      {i, 1, 3}] + Jintra Sum [IOps[[7, i]].IOps[[8, i]], {i, 1, 3}] +
     $\frac{\Sigma J}{2}$  (IOps[[1, 3]] + IOps[[2, 3]]) . (IOps[[3, 3]] + IOps[[4, 3]]) +
     $\frac{\Delta J}{2}$  (IOps[[1, 3]] - IOps[[2, 3]]) . (IOps[[3, 3]] - IOps[[4, 3]]) +
     $\frac{\Sigma J}{2}$  (IOps[[3, 3]] + IOps[[4, 3]]) . (IOps[[5, 3]] + IOps[[6, 3]]) +
     $\frac{\Delta J}{2}$  (IOps[[3, 3]] - IOps[[4, 3]]) . (IOps[[5, 3]] - IOps[[6, 3]]) +
     $\frac{\Sigma J}{2}$  (IOps[[5, 3]] + IOps[[6, 3]]) . (IOps[[7, 3]] + IOps[[8, 3]]) +
     $\frac{\Delta J}{2}$  (IOps[[5, 3]] - IOps[[6, 3]]) . (IOps[[7, 3]] - IOps[[8, 3]])
  );
  H
]

```

Setting up the basis for spin chain blocks

Calculations of expected frequencies of transitions in single-spin-inversion subspace

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 & |1\rangle & |2\rangle & |3\rangle & \dots & |n-1\rangle & |n\rangle \\
 |1\rangle & A & \Delta & & & & \\
 |2\rangle & \Delta & A & \Delta & & & \\
 |3\rangle & & \Delta & A & \Delta & & \\
 & & & \Delta & A & \Delta & \\
 \vdots & & & & \Delta & \ddots & \\
 & & & & & A & \Delta \\
 & & & & & \Delta & A & \Delta \\
 n-1\rangle & & & & & \Delta & A & \Delta \\
 |n\rangle & & & & & & \Delta & A
 \end{array}$$

$$\text{Coeff}[i_, k_, n_] := \sqrt{\frac{2}{n+1}} \sin\left[\frac{i k \pi}{n+1}\right];$$

(*Eigenvector coefficients for a chain of n coupled sites with nearest-neighbor interactions. i=site index, k=eigenmode index (k=1..n). Corresponds to Eq.(10) in the main text.*)

$$\text{EnergyM}[k_, \Delta_, A_, n_] := A + 2 \Delta \cos\left[\frac{k \pi}{n+1}\right];$$

(*Single-excitation eigenenergies for a chain of n coupled sites with uniform nearest-neighbor coupling Δ and energy offset A. Corresponds to Eq.(11) in the main text.*)

(*Calculating frequencies that are expected to appear in the spin-chain spectra when one assumes $\Delta J=5$ Hz, and a variable number of spins*)

```
In[*]:= (*2 spins*)
```

```
In[*]:= nspins = 2;
```

```
ΔJ = 5;
```

```
EnergyM[1, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins]
```

```
EnergyM[2, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins]
```

```
For[i = 2, i ≤ nspins, i++,
```

```
Print[EnergyM[1, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins] - EnergyM[i, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins]]
```

```
]
```

```
Out[*]=
5
2
```

```
Out[*]=
5
- 2
```

```
5
```

```
In[*]:= v21 = 5; (*Assigning transition frequency for plotting on the
spin chain spectra (n = 2). Frequencies are given in units of Hz*)
```

```
In[*]:= nspins = 3;
ΔJ = 5;
For[i = 1, i ≤ nspins, i++,
  Print[EnergyM[i, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins]]
]
For[i = 2, i ≤ nspins, i++,
  Print[EnergyM[1, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins] - EnergyM[i, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins] // N]
]

$$\frac{5}{\sqrt{2}}$$

0

$$-\frac{5}{\sqrt{2}}$$

3.53553
7.07107
```

```
In[*]:= v31 = 3.5355339059327373; (*Assigning transition frequencies for plotting
on the spin chain spectra (n = 3). Frequencies are given in units of Hz*)
v32 = 7.0710678118654755;
```

```
In[*]:= nspins = 4;
ΔJ = 5;
For[i = 1, i ≤ nspins, i++,
  Print[EnergyM[i, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins]]
]
Print[];
For[i = 1, i ≤ nspins, i++,
  For[j = i + 1, j ≤ nspins, j++,
    Print[EnergyM[i, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins] - EnergyM[j, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins] // N]
  ]
]
```

$$\frac{5}{4} \times (1 + \sqrt{5})$$

$$\frac{5}{4} \times (-1 + \sqrt{5})$$

$$\frac{5}{4} \times (1 - \sqrt{5})$$

$$\frac{5}{4} \times (-1 - \sqrt{5})$$

2.5

5.59017

8.09017

3.09017

5.59017

2.5

```
In[*]:= v41 = 2.5; (*Assigning transition frequencies for plotting on the spin chain spectra
           (n = 4). Frequencies are given in units of Hz and sorted in ascending order*)
v42 = 3.0901699437494745;
v43 = 5.5901699437494745;
v44 = 8.090169943749475;
```

```
In[*]:= nspins = 5;
        ΔJ = 5;
        For[i = 1, i ≤ nspins, i++,
            Print[EnergyM[i, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins]]
        ]
        Print[];
        For[i = 1, i ≤ nspins, i++,
            For[j = i + 1, j ≤ nspins, j++,
                Print[EnergyM[i, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins] - EnergyM[j, ΔJ / 2, 0, nspins] // N]
            ]
        ]
```

$$\frac{5\sqrt{3}}{2}$$
$$\frac{5}{2}$$
$$0$$
$$-\frac{5}{2}$$
$$-\frac{5\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

1.83013

4.33013

6.83013

8.66025

2.5

5.

6.83013

2.5

4.33013

1.83013

```
In[ ]:= v51 = 1.8301270189221928;  
(*Assigning transition frequencies for plotting on the spin chain spectra  
(n = 5). Frequencies are given in units of Hz and sorted in ascending order*)  
v52 = 2.5;  
v53 = 4.330127018922193;  
v54 = 5.0;  
v55 = 6.830127018922193;  
v56 = 8.660254037844386;
```

Calculation of spin-chain zero-quantum NMR for the case of 4 CH2 groups (full aliphatic chain Hamiltonian is considered below)

```

In[ ]:= BuildingBrasAndKets[StatesMz_, State_, Nspins_] :=
  Module[{State0, StateBra, StateKet},
    (*This function searches for the number of a target state that
      one wants to find e.g. {"S","S","S","T0"} in the basis of StatesMz,
      creates a vector with 1 at this position and then creates Ket
      (column vector) and Bra (row vector) representation of this function*)
    State0 = ConstantArray[0, {2Nspins}];
    State0[[Position[StatesMz, State][[1]][[1]]] = 1;
    StateBra = ArrayReshape[State0, {1, Length[State0]}];
    StateKet = ArrayReshape[State0, {Length[State0], 1}];
    {StateBra, StateKet}
  ]

In[ ]:= (* J-Couplings in aliphatic chain*)
Jintra := -14.0; (*add .0 after the number,
this is important for normalization of the eigenvectors*)
Jvic1 = 5.0;
Jvic2 = 10.0;

In[ ]:= ΔJ = Jvic2 - Jvic1;
ΣJ = Jvic2 + Jvic1;
τslic =  $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2} \Delta J}$ 

Out[ ]:= 0.141421

In[ ]:= Hj = HamIdealized[Jintra, ΣJ, ΔJ]
AbsoluteTiming[esysFreeEvolution = Eigensystem[Chop[Hj]]];
(*Calculating eigenstates and eigenenergies of a free precession Hamiltonian*)

Out[ ]:= {
  { ... 1 ... }
}

Out[ ]:= {0.0583655, Null}

In[ ]:= {SSST0Bra, SSST0Ket} = BuildingBrasAndKets[StatesMz, {"S", "S", "S", "T0"}, Nspins];
{SST0SBra, SST0SKet} = BuildingBrasAndKets[StatesMz, {"S", "S", "T0", "S"}, Nspins];
{ST0SSBra, ST0SSKet} = BuildingBrasAndKets[StatesMz, {"S", "T0", "S", "S"}, Nspins];
{T0SSSBra, T0SSSKet} = BuildingBrasAndKets[StatesMz, {"T0", "S", "S", "S"}, Nspins];

In[ ]:= (*Setting up ket.bra operators to initialize the density matrix
with nonuniform distribution of singlet and triplet product states.*)

```

```

In[ ]:= AbsoluteTiming[
  StateSSST0KetBra = Transpose[STBasisTransform].
    Transpose[MzTransform].SSST0Ket.SSST0Bra.MzTransform.STBasisTransform;
  StateSST0SKetBra = Transpose[STBasisTransform].Transpose[MzTransform].
    SST0SKet.SST0SBra.MzTransform.STBasisTransform;
  StateST0SSKetBra = Transpose[STBasisTransform].Transpose[MzTransform].
    ST0SSKet.ST0SSBra.MzTransform.STBasisTransform;
  StateT0SSSKetBra = Transpose[STBasisTransform].Transpose[MzTransform].
    T0SSSKet.T0SSSBra.MzTransform.STBasisTransform;]

Out[ ]:= {18.8863, Null}

(*Setting up initial state density operator with overpopulated |TSSS><TSSS|, |
  STSS><STSS|, |SSTS><SSTS| product singlet-triplet states and depopulated |
  SSST><SSST| state. This matrix corresponds to one flipped terminal fictitious spin-
  1/2 and the rest fictitious spins are in the alpha state.*)

In[ ]:= Rho0 = -StateSSST0KetBra + StateSST0SKetBra + StateST0SSKetBra + StateT0SSSKetBra;

In[ ]:= AbsoluteTiming[
  Rho0EigenBase =
    Chop[esysFreeEvolution[[2, All]].Rho0.ConjugateTranspose[esysFreeEvolution[[2, All]]]];
  SSST0KetBraEigenBase = Chop[esysFreeEvolution[[2, All]].
    StateSSST0KetBra.ConjugateTranspose[esysFreeEvolution[[2, All]]]];
  TwoSpinTraj12[t_] = ExpectationValue[Rho0EigenBase,
    SSST0KetBraEigenBase, esysFreeEvolution[[1, All], t];
  ]

Out[ ]:= {0.8369, Null}

(*Calculating time domain evolution of propagating singlet-triplet imbalances*)

In[ ]:= time = 20; (*Acquisition time*)
deltatime = 0.005; (*separation of points in time domain signals*)
AbsoluteTiming[
  TwoSpinTable12 = Chop[Table[Chop[TwoSpinTraj12[t]], {t, 0, time, deltatime}]];
  tvals = Parallelize[Table[t, {t, 0, time, deltatime}]]];]

Out[ ]:= {0.916845, Null}

(*Plotting spin-chain zero-quantum NMR spectra for the case of n =
  4 (number of CH2 groups), and initial state corresponding to  $\rho_0 = |
  TSSS\rangle\langle TSSS| + |STSS\rangle\langle STSS| + |SSTS\rangle\langle SSTS| - |SSST\rangle\langle SSST|$ . The processing
  and plotting routines are made with the assistance of ChatGPT.*)

In[ ]:= tvals = Range[0, time, deltatime];
(*points at which time domain signal is calculated*)
nPoints = Length[tvals]; (*total number of points in the time domain signal*)
dt = deltatime; (*separation of points in time domain*)
tau = 5.0; (*relaxation time*)

```

```

In[ ]:= process[data_] := Module[
  {demeaned, window, spec, half},

  (* subtract mean *)
  demeaned = data - Mean[data];

  (* exponential window *)
  window = Exp[-tvals / tau];

  (* Fourier transform *)
  spec = Fourier[demeaned * window, FourierParameters -> {1, -1}];

  (* keep only positive frequencies: first n/2 *)
  half = spec[[1 ;; Floor[nPoints / 2]]];

  half
]

In[ ]:= spec12 = process[TwoSpinTable12];

In[ ]:= v41 = 2.5; (*Assigning transition frequencies for plotting on the spin chain spectra
  (n = 4). Frequencies are given in units of Hz and sorted in ascending order*)
v42 = 3.0901699437494745;
v43 = 5.5901699437494745;
v44 = 8.090169943749475;

In[ ]:= Listfreqs4spins = {v41, v42, v43, v44};
transitions =
  Table[{Red, Dashed, Thick, Line[{{f, -250}, {f, 250}}]}, {f, Listfreqs4spins}];

In[ ]:= df = 1 / (nPoints * dt);
(*frequency resolution*) freqs = Range[0, df * (Floor[nPoints / 2] - 1), df];

In[ ]:= paperStyle = {Frame -> True, AspectRatio -> 0.6, (*square box*) ImageSize -> 360,
  (*pick a fixed size for consistency*) PlotRange -> {{0, 10.5}, All},
  FrameLabel -> {"Frequency (Hz)", None}, FrameStyle -> Directive[Black, Thick],
  (*thick axes/frame*) BaseStyle -> Directive[FontFamily -> "Helvetica", 16],
  LabelStyle -> Directive[Black, 18], (*label font*)
  FrameTicksStyle -> Directive[Black, 16], (*tick numbers font*)
  (*fewer ticks:coarse x ticks+automatic y ticks but reduced*)
  FrameTicks -> {{None, None}, (*{yLeft,yRight}*) {Range[0, 12, 2], None}
  (*{xBottom,xTop}*)}, (*helps prevent tons of minor ticks*)
  TicksStyle -> Directive[Black, Thick], PlotStyle -> Thick};

```

```

In[ ]:= ListLinePlot[
  Transpose[{freqs, Re[spec12]}],
  Evaluate@paperStyle, Epilog -> transitions
]

```


(*Spin-chain zero-quantum NMR spectrum that is shown in Fig. 6c of the manuscript*)

Spin-chain evolution in case if only two neighboring singlets are populated

```

In[ ]:= Rho0 = -StateSSST0KetBra - StateSST0SKetBra + StateST0SSKetBra + StateT0SSSKetBra;

```

```

In[ ]:= AbsoluteTiming[
  Rho0EigenBase =
    Chop[esysFreeEvolution[[2, All]].Rho0.ConjugateTranspose[esysFreeEvolution[[2, All]]]];
  SSST0KetBraEigenBase = Chop[esysFreeEvolution[[2, All]].
    StateSSST0KetBra .ConjugateTranspose[esysFreeEvolution[[2, All]]]];
  TwoSpinTraj12[t_] = ExpectationValue[Rho0EigenBase,
    SSST0KetBraEigenBase, esysFreeEvolution[[1, All]], t];
]

```

```

Out[ ]:= {0.852318, Null}

```

```

In[ ]:= time = 20;
deltatime = 0.005;
AbsoluteTiming[
  TwoSpinTable12 = Chop[Table[Chop[TwoSpinTraj12[t]], {t, 0, time, deltatime}]];
  tvals = Parallelize[Table[t, {t, 0, time, deltatime}]]];
]

```

```

Out[ ]:= {0.540608, Null}

```

```

In[ ]:= tvals = Range[0, time, deltatime];
n = Length[tvals];
dt = deltatime;

```

```

In[ ]:= tau = 5.0;

```

```

In[ ]:= process[data_] := Module[
  {demeaned, window, spec, half},

  (* subtract mean *)
  demeaned = data - Mean[data];

  (* exponential window *)
  window = Exp[-tvals / tau];

  (* Fourier transform *)
  spec = Fourier[demeaned * window, FourierParameters → {1, -1}];

  (* keep only positive frequencies: first n/2 *)
  half = spec[[1 ;; Floor[n / 2]]];

  half
]

In[ ]:= spec12 = process[TwoSpinTable12];

In[ ]:= df = 1 / (n * dt);
(*frequency resolution*) freqs = Range[0, df * (Floor[n / 2] - 1), df];

(*spin-chain zero-quantum spectrum shown in Fig 6d of the manuscript*)

In[ ]:= paperStyle = {Frame → True, AspectRatio → 0.6, (*square box*) ImageSize → 360,
  (*pick a fixed size for consistency*) PlotRange → {{0, 10.5}, All},
  FrameLabel → {"Frequency (Hz)", None}, FrameStyle → Directive[Black, Thick],
  (*thick axes/frame*) BaseStyle → Directive[FontFamily → "Helvetica", 16],
  LabelStyle → Directive[Black, 18], (*label font*)
  FrameTicksStyle → Directive[Black, 16], (*tick numbers font*)
  (*fewer ticks:coarse x ticks+automatic y ticks but reduced*)
  FrameTicks → {{None, None}, (*{yLeft,yRight}*) {Range[0, 12, 2], None}
  (*{xBottom,xTop}*)}, (*helps prevent tons of minor ticks*)
  TicksStyle → Directive[Black, Thick], PlotStyle → Thick};

```

```
In[ ]:= ListLinePlot[  
  Transpose[{freqs, Re[spec12]}],  
  Evaluate@paperStyle, Epilog -> transitions  
]
```

